

**BIO-MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS, GEOGRAPHICAL
DISTRIBUTION AND USE IN TRADITIONAL MEDICINE OF *CICHORIUM
INTYBUS***

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ABSTRACT

It is grown as a perennial or biennial plant. A plant with a straight stem, green, 15-150 cm tall. It is a plant belonging to the family of flowering plants. The leaves are arranged in a row. The flowers are pale, clustered in short panicles in the axils of the leaves, and collected in a single basket-like inflorescence at the end of the stem. The root is a taproot, which penetrates the soil to a depth of 1.5 m. It is propagated by seeds. It grows well in light fertile soils. Seeds are sown 2.5 cm deep, leaving a distance of 45 to 60 cm between them. Seeds develop quickly, usually 7 days, or 10 days. Usually 15 plants are left in 1 row.

Keywords: *Cichorium intybus, geographical distribution, traditional medicine, Frederick, Cichorium balearicum Porta, Cichorium byzantinum Clementi.*

Topic relevance: The history of the plant's use dates back to ancient Egypt. In ancient Rome, various dishes were prepared from this plant. Horace wrote about this in his memoirs, "Olives, mint and peppermint give me strength." In 1766, Frederick the Great banned the importation of coffee into Prussia, and now people began to use *Cichorium intybus* as a substitute for coffee. Based on this, in 1769 and 1770, these products began to be produced in Berlin and Prussia.

The purpose of the study. Wild pests eat and damage the plant, so it is necessary to protect it from pests. In the first year, the plant does not bloom, only a bunch of leaves is formed, but the root material can be prepared in autumn. It was found that the root of this plant, which is historically known as sachartqi, contains up to 40% inulin.

A number of tasks are identified based on the purpose of the study. In the United States, burdock root has long been used as a coffee substitute in prisons.[5] By the 1840s, the port of New Orleans was the second largest importer of coffee [7] During the American Civil War, when Union naval blockades cut off the port of New Orleans, Louisianans began adding sprigs to their coffee, creating a long-lasting and they created 'ana.

Scientific significance. In the 18th century, *Cichorium intybus* could be found in all states of North America and the USA. The collections collected in Canada show that there were originally nine local populations of the plant, 20 wild species in North America and 592 species and populations distributed in Eurasia. In addition to *Cichorium intybus*, *Cichorium balearicum* Porta, *Cichorium byzantinum* Clementi, *Cichorium caeruleum* Gilib, *Cichorium cicorea* Dumort, *Cichorium commune* Pall, *Cichorium cosnia* Buch.-Ham, *Cichorium divaricatum* Heldr. ex Nyman, *Cichorium glabratum* C. Presl, *Cichorium glaucum* Hoffmanns. Link, *Cichorium hirsutum* Gren, *Cichorium illyricum* borb, *Cichorium officinale* Gueldenst.Ledeb, *Cichorium perenne* Stokes, *Cichorium rigidum* Salisb., *Cichorium spinosum* Salisb., *Cichorium sylvestre* Garsault, *Cichorium sylvestre* Lam.

ANALYSIS OF THE LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT. From Eurasia, Scandinavia to the Mediterranean Sea and the British Isles, it can be found in Eastern Siberia and the Southern parts of India, and in the Northern parts of Africa. It can be found in the European part of Russia, the Caucasus and Siberia.

The common mushroom plant has been widely used in the Central Asian region of Kazakhstan in OIST disease, fever, inflammation and as a thirst quencher. There is a large amount of sachratki glycoside and inulin in the root of sachratki [8] This plant is valued as a medicinal plant in many countries of Eurasia and Africa. All parts are

widely used in traditional medicine. Important phytochemical substances are distributed in the plant, and it can be seen that the largest part of them is located in the roots of the plant. Since ancient times, people have widely used medicinal plants and began to have accurate information about their medicinal properties as a result of various experiments, and this information was passed down from generation to generation. Historically, the mushroom plant was first used by the Egyptians, and the regions where it was spread were identified. As a result, various preparations have been prepared from this plant and presented in a convenient way for use. For example, it is used to treat wounds in Turkey. In some countries, its tinctures are used. In European countries, it can be seen that the roots of *Cichorium intybus* are used in digestive diseases and to improve the digestion of food. Appetite is restored, digestion is improved. In Afghanistan, this plant was used in the treatment of various parasitic diseases, and these properties are scientifically based today. And in Italy, sources have arrived that are mainly used as tinctures. In India, *Cichorium intybus* is widely used among the population as a remedy for various liver diseases.

METHODOLOGY. The phytochemical composition of this plant and its importance in pharmacology have been widely studied. The reason for this is that the medicinal properties of the plant depend on its chemical composition. Based on this, more than 100 chemical compounds have been isolated from the plant, and they mainly belong to the root of the plant. In many regions of Pakistan, tinctures made from the root of the mushroom are used in diabetes. In this case, the roots are dried in the shade and ground into a powder. This powder is used twice a day with a glass of water before meals in order to reduce glucose levels.

CONCLUSION DISCUSSION. The research conducted in West Azerbaijan proved that local plants are of great importance for the health of the population. In the territory of Azerbaijan, the whole body parts of *Cichorium intybus* are used in the treatment of digestive problems, stomach pain, and removal of waste from the digestive tract. It is used to lower blood pressure and improve bile secretion. In Iran, the roots and stems of this plant are used to improve the secretion of bile, to treat the liver, and

in anime [4]. It has been shown to be used for the treatment of influenza with the help of a powder made from the root.

Research progress. Use of *Cichorium intybus* in traditional medicine. Countries Area of use in traditional medicine Plant part Preparation Source Afghanistan Malaria root Aqueous extract (Bischoff et al., 2004) Bosnia and Herzegovina diarrhoea, cancer, in reproductive organs Root, flowers, aerial part Not specified (Šarić-Kundalić et al., 2011) Bulgarian Root Decoction to Improve Gastric Secretion (Hanlidou et al., 2004) South Africa Hepatitis and liver diseases From leaf, stem, root Not specified (Van Wyk et al., 2009) Turkey Kidney stone, wound cleaning Root, leaf, surface.

CONCLUSION. Wild pests eat and damage the plant, so it is necessary to protect it from pests. In the first year, the plant does not bloom, only a bunch of leaves is formed, but the root material can be prepared in autumn. It was found that the root of this plant, which is historically known as sachartqi, contains up to 40% inilune [4]. The dictionary meaning of the word *Cichorium intybus* is "Cichoriu" which means field and "intybus" means to cut.

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